

A Theory of Information-Driven Expansion of The Universe

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Abstract

This document introduces a novel hypothesis linking the generation and growth of information in the universe to the phenomenon the accelerated expansion of the Universe. Drawing upon the **holographic principle**, this theory suggests that the universe's expansion is a direct consequence of increasing informational complexity, and that the dark energy comes into existence as a consequence of information generation, either serving as a mechanism for maintaining entropy balance within the universe, or as a medium for abstract information storage. The hypothesis also explores potential observational evidence, such as information-density-driven local variations in dark energy.

Introduction

Dark energy, constituting about 68% of the universe's total energy density, drives its accelerated expansion. However, its nature remains one of cosmology's greatest mysteries. This theory proposes a novel connection between dark energy and information, inspired by the holographic principle. This principle posits that the maximum amount of information that can be stored within a volume is proportional to the surface area enclosing it, rather than the volume itself.

The hypothesis introduces a new perspective: the universe's expansion is influenced by the total information generated, including physical processes, biological evolution, and the activities of advanced civilizations. The more information that exists, the greater the demand for spacetime "capacity," manifested as dark energy driving cosmic expansion.

Hypothesis

Core Idea:

The total information generated in the universe increases over time, and the universe expands to accommodate this new information. The holographic principle underpins this connection, suggesting that the expansion of spacetime (and dark energy's effective increase) corresponds

to the surface area required to store this information. Two explanations are possible for the role of the dark energy in this model:

- 1) Dark energy comes into existence as a part of mechanism for maintaining entropy balance;
- 2) Dark energy acts as a storage medium for information.

If Roger Penrose's theory of quantum consciousness proves correct, the brains of intelligent beings could serve as the crucial link between the generation of information and the physical processes responsible for the creation or utilization of dark energy. In this framework, consciousness—emerging from quantum processes in the brain—may bridge informational complexity with the underlying mechanisms of dark energy, either driving its generation as a medium for abstract information storage or maintaining cosmic entropy balance

Key Components:

1. Information Sources:

- **Physical Non-Biological Information:** Information generated by physical systems such as black holes, galaxies, and quantum phenomena.
- **Biological Non-Civilization Information:** The emergence and evolution of life contribute significantly to informational complexity. Brains of complex animals are the spots of high information concentration even at the level of the universe.
- **Civilizational Information:** Advanced civilizations generate vast amounts of information through technology, culture, and thought.

2. Holographic Principle and Dark Energy:

- The holographic principle limits the information density in any region of spacetime to the surface area enclosing it, linking the generation of information to the expansion of spacetime.
- As more information is generated, the "storage" or balance capacity of dark energy increases, driving universal expansion.

Implications

Dark Energy Evolution:

- Dark energy dominance (before ~ 7 Gyr) possibly coincides with a rapid growth in cosmic information, possibly linked to the emergence of galaxies, complex structures, or early forms of life.

Local Hotspots of Dark Energy:

- Advanced civilizations or other regions of high entropy should contribute disproportionately to information generation, potentially causing localized increases

in dark energy density. If these "information hotspots" could be observable in this manner, we might obtain useful new knowledge about our potential neighbors.

Conclusion

This hypothesis reimagines the relationship between information, spacetime, and dark energy through the lens of the holographic principle. By linking information generation to the dynamics of dark energy, it provides a potential explanation for the universe's accelerated expansion. Future research should outline the mathematical framework, simulate cosmic information dynamics, and identify observational evidence to support or refute the theory.

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